

ISic1375

I.Sicily inscription 1375

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 296

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ἐνθάδεκεῖται]

2. Δι[ον][υσι][ζήσασ][]

3. ἀμέμπτως [ἔτη]

4. λε τελευτᾷ τ[ῆ]πρ(ὸ)---

5. νωνῶν Σε[πτ](εμβρίων) [ἡμέ]

6. ρα Κυρίου ἐ[ν εἰρήνῃ]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Here lies Dionysos/Dionysios, having lived blameless for 35 years, for he died [?] day before the [?] of September. Of his master, in peace.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492989

EDCS 39101756

PHI 140881

PHI 316263

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1375. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4353565>